

Current status and distribution of alien land snails and slugs in Greece

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Abstract. Alien species, those that have been introduced on purpose or by accident to an ecosystem that they do not naturally occur, may cause serious damages to their new environment. So far, our knowledge of alien land snails and slugs in Greece is limited. We performed a literature survey and recorded all occurrences of alien terrestrial gastropod species in Greece and supplemented our effort with observations from the iNaturalist platform. In total, we documented 91 literature records and iNaturalist observations of at least 11 alien species of land snails and slugs recorded throughout Greece for the period 1973–2024. The documented alien species are: *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834), *Paralaoma servilis* (Shuttleworth, 1852), *Gonyodiscus rotundatus* (O.F. Müller, 1774), *Lucilla singleyana* (Pilsbry, 1889), *Zonitoides arboreus* (Say, 1817), *Hawaiiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1841), *Polygyra cereolus* (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1818), *Ambigolimax parvipenis* Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022, *A. valentianus* (A. Férussac, 1821), *Boettgerilla pallens* Simroth, 1912, and *Deroceras invadens* Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011. A systematic survey for alien terrestrial gastropods in Greece is pressing. Greenhouses, botanical gardens, cultivated land, plant nurseries, and heavily disturbed habitats should be the first sites for investigation. We propose the involvement of citizen scientists in the search for alien species in order to speed up the surveys and to collect data from geographically isolated sites such as the Greek islands. Our work is a contribution to the knowledge of alien species of Greece.

Key words. Terrestrial gastropods, literature records, iNaturalist, citizen science, species distribution

Περίληψη. Τα ξενικά είδη, είδη τα οποία έχουν εισαχθεί σκοπίμως ή κατά λάθος σε ένα οικοσύστημα εκτός του φυσικού τους εύρους εξάπλωσης, μπορούν να επιφέρουν σοβαρές καταστροφές στο νέο τους περιβάλλον. Ως τώρα, η γνώση μας για τα ξενικά χερσαία γαστερόποδα που απαντούν στην Ελλάδα είναι περιορισμένη. Στην παρούσα εργασία πραγματοποιήσαμε βιβλιογραφική ανασκόπηση και καταγράψαμε όλα τα ξενικά χερσαία γαστερόποδα, τα οποία έχουν αναφερθεί από την Ελλάδα. Η έρευνά μας συμπληρώθηκε με παρατηρήσεις από την ηλεκτρονική πλατφόρμα iNaturalist. Συνολικά, συγκεντρώσαμε 91 βιβλιογραφικές αναφορές και παρατηρήσεις από την ηλεκτρονική πλατφόρμα iNaturalist για τουλάχιστον 11 ξενικά είδη χερσαίων γαστερόποδων τα οποία έχουν καταγραφεί στην Ελλάδα μεταξύ 1973–2024. Τα ξενικά είδη που καταγράφηκαν είναι τα εξής: *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834), *Paralaoma servilis* (Shuttleworth, 1852), *Gonyodiscus rotundatus* (O.F. Müller, 1774), *Lucilla singleyana* (Pilsbry, 1889), *Zonitoides arboreus* (Say, 1817), *Hawaiiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1841), *Polygyra cereolus* (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1818), *Ambigolimax parvipenis* Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022, *A. valentianus* (A. Férussac, 1821), *Boettgerilla pallens* Simroth, 1912 και *Deroceras invadens* Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011. Καταλήγουμε πως υπάρχει επιτακτική ανάγκη για συστηματική έρευνα σχετικά με τα ξενικά χερσαία γαστερόποδα στην Ελλάδα. Προτείνουμε οι πρώτες περιοχές διερεύνησης για ξενικά είδη να συμπεριλαμβάνουν θερμοκήπια, βοτανικούς κήπους, καλλιεργούμενες εκτάσεις, φυτώρια και έντονα διαταραγμένους βιοτόπους. Επίσης, η ενεργή συμμετοχή των πολιτών–επιστημόνων στην αναζήτηση ξενικών ειδών θα επιταχύνει την ερευνητική προσπάθεια και τη συλλογή δεδομένων από γεωγραφικά απομονωμένες περιοχές, όπως τα ελληνικά νησιά. Η παρούσα εργασία αποτελεί σημαντική συμβολή στην αύξηση της γνώσης που αφορά στα ξενικά χερσαία γαστερόποδα της Ελλάδας.

Λέξεις-κλειδιά. χερσαία γαστερόποδα, βιβλιογραφικές αναφορές, iNaturalist, επιστήμη των πολιτών, κατανομές ειδών

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INTRODUCTION

Global species translocation has increased in the last ca 200 years (Seebens *et al.* 2017). Various pathways of species introduction to new environments mediated by human activities are recognised, including intentional releases of animals (e.g. for pest control) and escapes from captivity or via the trade of goods, plants, and garden soils across the globe (e.g. Pyšek *et al.* 2020; Seebens *et al.* 2017; Polce *et al.* 2023). According to EU Regulation 1143/2014, alien species are defined as “a species ... introduced outside its natural range ... that might survive and reproduce”. The same regulation states that gametes, seeds, eggs, propagules, hybrids, varieties, or breeds may as well be characterized as alien species. In addition, EU Regulation 1143/2014 describes invasive alien species as “species whose introduction or spread threatens or impacts upon biodiversity and related ecosystem services”. To assist in the exploration and support access to information of alien species occurring in Europe, the European Alien Species Information Network (EASIN) was established by the European Commission (Katsanevakis *et al.* 2015).

Land snails and slugs are passively transported by humans with soil and plants, or carried by vehicles and containers (Dörge *et al.* 1999; Horsák *et al.* 2020). Two species of land snails, *Lissachatina fulica* (Bowdich, 1822) and *Euglandina rosea* (A. Férussac, 1821), are included in the list of the 100 worst invasive worldwide (Lowe *et al.* 2000). The list of invasive alien species of Union Concern (v. 2025) (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02016R1141-20250807>) does not include any land snails, although over the years the number of alien land-snail species in Europe keeps growing (e.g. von Proschwitz 2004; Horsák *et al.* 2020). Many of the alien species have been mostly recorded from greenhouses, botanical gardens, or parks, and they arrive from outside of Europe (for a review see Hausdorf 2023; Walker 2025). Other alien land snails are European species that have been transported outside their natural range and have established viable populations in new areas (e.g. Ronsmans & Van den Neucker 2016). For example, *Limacus maculatus* (Kaleniczenko, 1851) is a native slug of the Black Sea region which has lately been spreading across Central Europe (e.g. Turóci *et al.* 2023 and references therein). Similarly, *Tandonia kusceri* (H. Wagner, 1931), a slug which is native to the Western Balkans, was recently discovered in Vienna, Austria (Duda *et al.* 2022).

Throughout Europe there is an ongoing attempt to record and identify specimens of alien gastropods and track the possible pathways of their introduction (e.g. von Proschwitz 2004; Čiliak *et al.* 2016; Horsák *et al.* 2020; Richling & von

Proschwitz 2021; Duda *et al.* 2022; Turóci *et al.* 2023; Walker 2025). In a few countries the effort stretches over the last two decades (Peltanová *et al.* 2012) and as a result reliable lists of alien species have been compiled, and regular monitoring takes place in areas where alien species have been recorded (Horsák *et al.* 2013; Čejka *et al.* 2020; Horsák *et al.* 2025). Most recently, alien species have been identified through citizen-science projects (e.g. Hungary) making the procedure of locating alien species less time consuming and more cost efficient (e.g. Páll-Gergely *et al.* 2019; Turóci *et al.* 2023).

So far, our knowledge of alien land snails and slugs in Greece is restricted. A recent collective effort produced the first report on the “Invasive Alien Species” (IAS) of Greece (Arianoutsou *et al.* 2023), which however, did not include land molluscs. Another recent work on invasive alien species of Greece stresses the lack of knowledge on alien land snail and slugs in our country (Korakaki *et al.* 2021). Until recently, five species were known to occur in Greece: *Boettgerilla pallens* Simroth, 1912, *Deroceras invadens* Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011, *Ambigolimax valentianus* (A. Férussac, 1821), *Hawaiiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1841), and *Zonitoides nitidus* (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Vardinoyannis *et al.* 2020). Furthermore, Hutchinson *et al.* (2022) described a new potentially alien species, *Ambigolimax parvipenis* Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022, with Athens as one of its known localities. The latest addition to Greece’s list of alien land snails is the account of *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834) from the island of Crete (Zeimbekis *et al.* 2023).

Our aim is to update the current state of knowledge regarding alien terrestrial molluscs of Greece. We compiled a comprehensive list of occurrences of alien land snails and slugs documented from Greece, draw distribution maps, and discuss future research steps.

METHODS

The published literature of the 20th and 21st centuries (i.e. since 1900) on Greek land snails and slugs was searched and occurrences of alien species were recorded. Data on collection dates, habitats, and other information relevant to the species’ ecology were gathered, and distribution maps of the alien species in Greece were created using ArcGIS Pro v. 10. We provide a synonymic list for each species, which includes bibliographic references of the species from Greece; the lists of synonyms for each species are not intended to be complete outside of the literature for Greece. Herein, alien terrestrial molluscs were considered the species complying with the definition of alien species provided by EU Regulation 1143/2014 and have not been considered as part of

the native land-snail Greek fauna. In determining which species are native, we consulted reliable sources on Greek land snails, such as Welter-Schultes (2012) and Vardinoyannis et al. (2020). Furthermore, we supplemented our research effort with observations of alien molluscs that we retrieved from the iNaturalist up to September 2024 (<https://greece.inaturalist.org>, <https://inaturalist.org>).

RESULTS

Our literature review revealed 62 records of 10 alien species scattered over mainland and insular Greece (Fig. 1, Tables 1, A1). In addition, searching of iNaturalist added 29 more records belonging to at least three alien species: *Ambigolimax* sp., *Paralaoma servilis* (Shuttleworth, 1852), and *Polygyra cereolus* (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1818) (Fig. 1, Tables

1, A2). Thus, in total, 11 alien species of terrestrial molluscs were documented: *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834), *P. servilis* (Shuttleworth, 1852), *Gonyodiscus rotundatus* (O.F. Müller, 1774), *Lucilla singleyana* (Pilsbry, 1889), *Zonitoides arboreus* (Say, 1817), *Hawaiiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1841), *P. cereolus* (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1818), *Ambigolimax parvipenis* Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022, *A. valentianus* (A. Férussac, 1821), *Boettgerilla pallens* Simroth, 1912, and *Deroceras invadens* Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011. The alien species belonged to 10 families. Four species were slugs (*A. valentianus*, *A. parvipenis*, *B. pallens*, and *D. invadens*). The most widespread species and with the greatest number of records (47 in total) was *P. servilis* (Fig. 2). The taxon with the highest number of observations (25) in iNaturalist was *Ambigolimax* sp. All iNaturalist observations of *A. valentianus* were treated as *Ambigolimax* sp., as a reliable identification

Figure 1. Literature records and iNaturalist observations of alien land snails and slugs in Greece.

Table 1. List of alien species of land snails and slugs in Greece. A detailed list of the bibliographic records and the iNaturalist observations is provided in the Appendix, Tables A1 and A2.

Species	Bibliographic record	iNaturalist observation
<i>Allopeas gracile</i>	1	
<i>Paralaoma servilis</i>	44	3
<i>Gonyodiscus rotundatus</i>	2	
<i>Lucilla singleyana</i>	6	
<i>Zonitoides arboreus</i>	1	
<i>Hawaiiia minuscula</i>	2	
<i>Polygyra cereolus</i>		1
<i>Ambigolimax parvipenis</i>	1	
<i>Ambigolimax valentianus</i>	3	
<i>Ambigolimax</i> sp.		25
<i>Boettgerilla pallens</i>	1	
<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	1	

to the species level can be achieved by the study of its genital anatomy (see Hutchinson *et al.* 2022 for details).

LIST OF ALIEN LAND MOLLUSCS DOCUMENTED FROM GREECE

Family Achatinidae Swainson, 1840

Genus *Allopeas* Baker, 1935

1. *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834)

Allopeas gracile—Zeimbekis *et al.* 2023: 43, fig. 2.

Origin. Old World tropics (?) (for a discussion on the species' origin, see Horsák *et al.* 2020; Hausdorf 2023 and references therein).

Remarks. *Allopeas gracile* was collected from a river estuary in north-western Crete (Zeimbekis *et al.* 2023) (Fig. 2). The species has been identified from a few sites around Europe, e.g. in England (Preece & White 2012), Germany (Jaekel & Plate 1967), and Austria (Reischütz 2012). The record from Greece was not associated with a botanical garden, contrary to previous finds of the species in Europe (e.g. Jaekel & Plate 1967; Preece & White 2012; Reischütz 2012; Horsák *et al.* 2020), although the possibility that the shell came from a nearby greenhouse cannot be excluded. Reviews of the distribution and current status of *A. gracile* in Europe hint that it is expanding its range across the continent (Horsák *et al.* 2020; Hausdorf 2023).

Family Punctidae Morse, 1864

Genus *Paralaoma* Iredale, 1913

2. *Paralaoma servilis* (Shuttleworth, 1852)

Pleuropunctum micropleuros—Falkner 1974: 239.

Toltecia pusilla—Reischütz 1983: 135; Reischütz 1985: 302; Reischütz 1986: 94–95, 101; Bank and Neuteboom 1988: 58; Reischütz 1988: 345.

Paralaoma caputspinulae—Bank & Maassen 1998: 55; Reischütz & Reischütz 2004: 3; Reischütz *et al.* 2010: 33.

Paralaoma servilis—Reischütz & Reischütz 2009b: 44; Georgiev & Stoycheva 2010: 74, table 1; Reischütz *et al.* 2014: 70; Reischütz *et al.* 2015: 71; Georgiev & Ivanova 2015: 72, table 2; Reischütz *et al.* 2016: 73; Georgiev 2016: 30, table 2; Georgiev *et al.* 2018: 18, table 2; Reischütz & Reischütz 2020: 70; Maroulis *et al.* 2022: 9, supplementary table 1.

Origin. Southwestern Pacific Rim (?). A recent phylogenetic review of *P. servilis* revealed that there are at least five distinct species with different origins lumped under the name *P. servilis* (Nekola *et al.* 2025). *Paralaoma servilis* most probably originated in south-eastern Australia and has expanded its distribution to North America, Europe, and Macaronesia in the Atlantic Ocean. For an extended discussion on the species' origin, see Nekola *et al.* (2025).

Remarks. *Paralaoma servilis* is widespread throughout mainland Greece (Fig. 2), but it also has been reported from Thasos, Samothraki, and Limnos islands in the North Aegean (Reischütz 1983; Reischütz 1985), Samos and Nisyros islands in south-eastern Aegean (Bank & Neuteboom 1988; Bank & Maassen 1998), and most recently from Kea island in the Cyclades (Maroulis *et al.* 2022). On Samos, established populations appear to be persisting, as it was reported from multiple localities (Bank & Maassen 1998). Recent phylogenetic analyses indicate that *P. servilis* *s.l.* is present in western Europe, but no samples of the taxon were analysed from the eastern Mediterranean region (Nekola *et al.* 2025). Thus, at the moment, it is not possible to determine which clade or clades are present in Greece.

Family Discidae Thiele, 1931 (1866)

Genus *Gonyodiscus* Fitzinger, 1833

3. *Gonyodiscus rotundatus* (O.F. Müller, 1774)

Discus rotundatus—Reischütz *et al.* 2015: 71–72; Reischütz & Reischütz 2019: 98, fig. 1.

Origin. Western and central Europe (Kuznik-Kowalska 1999; Welter-Schultes 2012; Salvador, Ravalo and de Winter 2023).

Figure 2. Distribution of records of the alien species *A. gracile*, *B. pallens*, *P. servilis* and *P. cereolus*.

Remarks. This species was found in river deposits in south Peloponnese (Reischütz *et al.* 2015; Reischütz & Reischütz 2019), and to our knowledge these are the only records from Greece (Fig. 3). The Southern Balkans are not part of the known distribution of *G. rotundatus* (Kužnik-Kowalska 1999; Welter-Schultes 2012) All the above indicate that *G. rotundatus* was introduced to Greece and therefore is considered an alien species.

Family Helicodiscidae Pilsbry, 1927

Genus *Lucilla* Lowe, 1852

4. *Lucilla singleyana* (Pilsbry, 1889)

Lucilla singleyana—Reischütz *et al.* 2008: 6; Reischütz *et al.*

2015: 71; Reischütz *et al.* 2016: 73; Reischütz & Reischütz 2020: 70.

Lucilla scintilla [= *Helicodiscus singleyanus*]—Reischütz & Reischütz 2009b: 44.

Origin. North America (Horsák *et al.* 2009; Thompson 2011).

Remarks. Reischütz & Reischütz (2009b) collected *Lucilla scintilla* (Lowe, 1852) from an irrigation channel in central Greece. In Greece, *L. singleyana* has always been reported from the vicinity of river bodies or water channels (e.g. Reischütz & Reischütz 2020). The earliest Greek record is from 2004 (Reischütz & Reischütz 2009b) and not 2006, as erroneously reported by Hausdorf (2023). *Lucilla singleyana* is currently known only from the Greek mainland (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Distribution of records of the alien species *D. invadens*, *G. rotundatus*, *L. singleyana* and *H. minuscula*.

Family Gastrodontiidae Tryon, 1866

Genus *Zonitoides* Lehmann, 1862

5. *Zonitoides arboreus* (Say, 1817)

Zonitoides arboreus—Reischütz & Reischütz 2020: 70.

Origin. North and Central America (Hubricht 1985; Thompson 2011).

Remarks. *Zonitoides arboreus* was collected from the deposits of river Sperchios in central Greece in 2019 (Reischütz & Reischütz 2020) (Fig. 4). There are recent observations of *Z. arboreus* from the neighbouring countries of Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Italy (Hausdorf 2023). Out-

side its native distribution, the species is commonly found in large numbers in greenhouses (e.g. Horsák *et al.* 2004), but recently surviving populations were observed outdoors (e.g. Dvořák & Kupka 2007). So far, we cannot exclude the possibility that *Z. arboreus* was washed out by the river Sperchios from surrounding cultivated land, and more research is required to determine the origins of the stream-drift shells in the river Sperchios.

Another record of *Zonitoides* sp. from northern Greece was recorded by Sattmann & Reischütz (1988) from Stomio, Larissa. The record is not included here, as it is uncertain whether it belongs to *Z. arboreus* or another species, *Z. nitidus* (O.F. Müller, 1774).

Figure 4. Distribution of records of the alien taxa *A. parvipenis*, *A. valentianus*, *Ambigolimax* sp. and *Z. arboreus*.

Family Pristilomatidae Cockerell, 1891

Genus *Hawaiiia* Gude, 1911

6. *Hawaiiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1841)

Hawaiiia minuscula—Reischütz & Reischütz 2009a: 41; Reischütz & Reischütz 2020: 70.

Origin. North and Central America (Hubricht 1985; Thompson 2011).

Remarks. Two records of *H. minuscula* are known from Greece so far. Two empty shells were collected from a plant nursery in western Greece (Reischütz & Reischütz 2009a), and an unknown number of shells was collected from a stream in central Greece (Reischütz & Reischütz 2020). In Europe the species has been usually spotted in botanical

gardens or greenhouses (e.g. Horsák *et al.* 2004; Čiliak *et al.* 2016; Walker 2025).

Family Polygyridae Pilsbry, 1895

Genus *Polygyra* Say, 1818

7. *Polygyra cereolus* (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1818)

Origin. Southern North America (Hubricht 1985; Thompson 2011).

Remarks. *Polygyra cereolus* was recorded from Rhodos island in the south-eastern Aegean Archipelago (Fig. 2). There is a single Greek record of this species, observed in 2020, in the iNaturalist platform. *Polygyra cereolus* has already been introduced to other Mediterranean countries (Hausdorf 2023).

Family Limacidae Batsch, 1789

Genus *Ambigolimax* (Pollonera, 1887)

8. *Ambigolimax valentianus* (A. Férussac, 1821)

Lehmannia valentiana (Férussac, 1822)—Reischütz *et al.* 2011: 55, fig. 2.

Ambigolimax valentianus (Férussac, 1822)—Rowson *et al.* 2014: table S1.

Lehmannia valentiana (Férussac, 1823)—Triantis *et al.* 2008: 474, table 1.

Origin. The earliest discovery of this species in the Iberian Peninsula suggests that the species originated there or perhaps Western Africa (Wiktor *et al.* 2000; Turóci *et al.* 2023). However, at the moment, there is no evidence that validates this suggestion (Turóci *et al.* 2023).

Remarks. *Ambigolimax valentianus* was reported from three geographically separated localities in northern Greece (Reischütz *et al.* 2011), Skyros island in the central Aegean Archipelago (Triantis *et al.* 2008), and Crete in the southern Aegean Archipelago (Rowson *et al.* 2014) (Fig. 4). *Ambigolimax valentianus* has been found in the neighbouring countries of Serbia (Stojnić *et al.* 2011) and Turkey (Ekin & Şeşen 2018). This species is widespread throughout Europe (Stojnić *et al.* 2011; Turóci *et al.* 2023) and worldwide (Wiktor *et al.* 2000).

9. *Ambigolimax parvipenis* Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022

Ambigolimax parvipenis Hutchinson *et al.* 2022: 40–41, fig. 10F.

Origin. Unknown (Hutchinson *et al.* 2022).

Remarks. In Greece, *A. parvipenis* was reported from a single locality in the centre of Athens (Hutchinson *et al.* 2022). It is considered an invasive species, although its origin remains elusive (Hutchinson *et al.* 2022). The presence of *A. parvipenis* has been validated in Europe (Greece, the British Isles, France, the Iberian Peninsula, Canary Islands, Chafarinas Islands off the coast of Africa), and North America (California, Arizona) (Hutchinson *et al.* 2022).

***Ambigolimax* sp.**

Remarks. All iNaturalist observations (Table A2) are treated here as *Ambigolimax* sp. since reliable identification to species relies on the study of the genital system (Hutchinson *et al.* 2022). These observations are evidence that *Ambigolimax* is widespread all over Greece (Fig. 4).

Family Boettgerillidae Wiktor & Likharev, 1979

Genus *Boettgerilla* Simroth, 1910

10. *Boettgerilla pallens* Simroth, 1912

Boettgerilla pallens—Reischütz *et al.* 2011: 55, fig. 1.

Origin. Caucasus (Reise *et al.* 2000).

Remarks. A single record of *B. pallens* is mentioned from Axios river in north-central Greece where this species was collected from under boards in a meadow (Reischütz *et al.* 2011) (Fig. 2).

Family Agriolimacidae H. Wagner, 1935

Genus *Deroceras* Rafinesque, 1820

11. *Deroceras invadens* Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011

Deroceras invadens—Rowson *et al.* 2014: table S1

Origin. Italy (Reise *et al.* 2011).

Remarks. *Deroceras invadens* was collected from a disturbed shrubland in a seaside tourist site in Crete (Rowson *et al.* 2014) (Fig. 3). It is a synanthrope and is now widespread around the world (Hutchinson *et al.* 2014, 2020; Turóci *et al.* 2023).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this study we documented 11 species of alien land snails and slugs from Greece and expanded our knowledge of their distribution across the country. The origins of the alien land snails and slugs found in Greece are diverse, having come from North and South America, South East Asia, or elsewhere in Europe. Through a comprehensive review of published bibliography and citizen-science observations on the iNaturalist platform, we gathered 91 records that span 52 years (1973–2024).

Despite the lack of systematic research efforts for alien terrestrial gastropods in Greece, there is a growing list of alien species (Vardinoyannis *et al.* 2020; Hausdorf 2023). The earliest discovery of an alien land snail, *P. servilis*, in Greece is from the Peloponnese in 1973 (Falkner 1974). *Paralaoma servilis* was the most commonly documented and most widespread alien species both in mainland and insular Greece. Its distribution pattern suggests that this species has successfully colonised the country in a span of approximately 50 years.

It is important to note that alien land snails and slugs, such as *A. gracile*, *P. servilis*, *P. cereolus*, *A. valentianus*, and

D. invadens, have already arrived even in the geographically isolated Greek islands. *Allopeas gracile*, is a well-known alien land snail in Europe and has been documented, so far, from several other European countries, mainly found in greenhouses and botanical gardens (e.g. Jaeckel & Plate 1967; Preece & White 2012; Reischütz 2012). However, in Greece, *A. gracile* was found in a natural habitat (a river estuary), contrary elsewhere in Europe (e.g. Jaeckel & Plate 1967; Preece & White 2012; Reischütz *et al.* 2012; Reischütz 2012; Horsák *et al.* 2020).

The characteristic three bands of the genus *Ambigolimax* make the genus identification relatively easy, while the study of its genitalia is required for a species-level identification (Hutchinson *et al.* 2022). Observations in iNaturalist, which cannot be identified to species, indicate *Ambigolimax* is rather widespread in Greece. So far, the presence of *A. parvipenis* in Greece is based on a single record from an urban park in Athens (Hutchinson *et al.* 2022), while *A. valentianus*, has been found in natural habitats in Greece (e.g. Reischütz *et al.* 2011). Thus, the anatomical study of the Greek *Ambigolimax* spp. is required to identify the extent to which these species occur in Greece.

The disparity of data on alien land snails and slugs in Greece may reflect the lack of research effort focused on anthropogenic habitats or areas heavily affected by humans. Our results infer that the first alien species arrived in Greece later compared to other European countries (see Hausdorf 2023 for a comparison). However, we cannot exclude the possibility that alien terrestrial gastropods may have gone unnoticed for some time. For example, *Gonyodiscus rotundatus* was recorded for the first time from Greece in 2014 (Reischütz *et al.* 2015) but reported from the neighbouring Turkey more than a decade earlier (Örstan 2003). Though this species occurs in neighbouring countries (Welter-Schultes 2012), its single, isolated occurrence in Greece suggests a recent introduction.

Citizen science has proved to be an invaluable tool in the research of alien species in general (e.g. Zenetos *et al.* 2013; Barahona-Segovia *et al.* 2024). The involvement of citizen scientists, or at least the consideration and potential use of alien species posts on online platforms, has been successfully used (e.g. Turóci *et al.* 2023; Barahona-Segovia *et al.* 2024). The complementary value of iNaturalist data, which added 29 records and two additional species not reported from Greece in literature alone, highlights the growing utility of citizen science in biodiversity monitoring. We anticipate that organised efforts (e.g. bioblitzes) focusing on finding alien land snails and slugs will assist in filling gaps in alien species' distributions in Greece. Establishing a net-

work of citizen scientists would be a cost-efficient, fast way to collect data from around Greece, especially from geographically distant or isolated places like the Greek islands. Of course, the data collected through a network of citizen scientists will have to be validated by expert scientists, as in many cases, the identification of species requires the study of their genital anatomy or the use of molecular tools.

Our knowledge on alien land snails and slugs is limited, and the invasion patterns have not been studied at all compared to other taxa of alien species (e.g. Arianoutsou *et al.* 2010; Korakaki *et al.* 2021; Arianoutsou *et al.* 2023). Furthermore, the impact of alien terrestrial gastropods in Greece remains poorly explored, despite the increasing efforts to document alien biodiversity inside the country (e.g. Arianoutsou *et al.* 2023). The presence of alien terrestrial gastropods in Greece should be investigated, and the detection and monitoring of potentially established populations, should be a priority in future studies.

This work is the first systematic attempt to compile and georeference all known records of alien land snails and slugs in Greece. Future research efforts should focus on the validation of the literature records through fieldwork to confirm the presence or persistence of populations in the country. Furthermore, the interactions of alien gastropods with the native fauna and flora should be evaluated and the status of aliens, or worse invasives, should be determined.

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APPENDIX

Table A1. List of literature records of alien land snails and slugs reported from Greece. The numbers in the first column refer to the numbered species in the main text. When the name used in the literature differs from currently used name, it is noted with the literature reference.

No.	Species	Location	Collection date	Literature reference	Lat. (°N)	Long. (°E)
ACHATINIDAE						
1	<i>Allopeas gracile</i>	Souda Bay, Chania, banks of Moronis river	01/2020	Zeimbekis <i>et al.</i> 2023	35.4939	24.0611
PUNCTIDAE						
2	<i>Paralaoma servilis</i>	River deposits of Spercheios N of Kostalexis (W of Lamia, Fthiotida, Greece)	09/2019	Reischütz & Reischütz 2020	38.8679	22.3622
		Kalamata, deposits of river Nedonas	04/2014	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2015	37.0422	22.1131
		NE slope of Pangaion Mountains near Nikissiani	08/1982	Reischütz 1985, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.9444	24.1312
		Samothraki island. Palaiopolis on Agios Georgios	07/1984	Reischütz 1985, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.4740	25.5589
		Limnos island. Sand dunes on shore of Limni Aliki, NE tip of Limnos; location 25 in Reischütz (1986)	08/1984	Reischütz 1985, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	39.9555	25.3668
		Limnos island. Gorges on N slope of castle hill of Myrina; location 1b in Reischütz (1986)	08/1984	Reischütz 1985, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	39.8780	25.0552
		1. Bigger canal between Trichonida and Lysimachia Lakes	08/2003	Reischütz & Reischütz 2009b	38.5501	21.4259
		2. Canal between Boutsia and Patoulia N of Lake Lysimachia	07/2004	Reischütz & Reischütz 2009b	38.6114	21.3462
		1. Pamissos spring in Agios Floros	07/2009	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2010, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.1691	22.0248
		2. Irrigation channel on right bank of Pamissos about 500 m above bridge on road from Kalamata to Messini	07/2009	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2010, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.0521	22.0204
		3. Excavation site of Pamissos at bridge on Kalamata–Messini road	07/2007	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2010, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.0513	22.0211
		4. Beds of Pamissos near bridge on Kalamata Messini road	07/2009	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2010, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.0540	22.0208
		5. Ditch on right-bank of Pamissos	07/2009	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2010, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.0509	22.0208
		27. Venetian tower on seafront between Arsanas Zografou and Arsanas Konstamonitou	09/2013	Reischütz & Reischütz 2014	40.2838	24.1573
		Dam of Alfios river near Olympia	07/2004	Reischütz & Reischütz 2004, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.6361	21.5821
		7. Olive groves S of Aliki	08/1982	Reischütz 1983, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.6049	24.7364
		Palaiopolis (Paleopoli), samples from Heroion	07/1984	Reischütz 1986, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.5012	25.5305
		4. Source on Olymbiada–Arnea road N of junction to Varvara. Crystalline rocks and marble	1985	Reischütz 1988, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.5575	23.6874
		11. Gorge below Moni Ikosifinissos, Pangaion. Marble	1982	Reischütz 1988, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.9657	24.1051
		61b. Chora of Samothraki, ruins	1985	Reischütz 1988, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.4753	25.5250
		VI. Chora, limestone rocks by Katsabas stream	04/1986	Reischütz 1988, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	40.4827	25.5171

Table A1. Continued.

No.	Species	Location	Collection date	Literature reference	Lat. (°N)	Long. (°E)
2	<i>Paralaoma servilis</i>	Agia Marina. Around the monastery, shrubland, old cultivations and temporary stream, limestone	11/2021	Maroulis <i>et al.</i> 2022	37.6174	24.3024
		Poles. Archaeological site and temporary stream with phrygana, abandoned cultivations; calcareous rocks	11/2021	Maroulis <i>et al.</i> 2022	37.5597	24.3296
		24. Maquis near road to Dionis temple	06/2015	Georgiev & Ivanova 2015	40.8807	25.5176
		Location 9 Samothraki island. At a small, canalized river west of Alonia	08/2008	Georgiev & Stoycheva 2010	40.4546	25.4956
		Location 17 Samothraki island. Above (S of) Palaiopolis	08/2008	Georgiev & Stoycheva 2010	40.4993	25.5295
		Moni Evangelistria W of Marathokambos 550 m	1991, 1993	Bank & Maassen 1998, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.7147	26.6402
		Crossroad of Avlakia, Agios Konstantinos and Manolates, 0.5 km towards Manolates, rock wall between Platanakia and Valeontates	1991, 1993	Bank & Maassen 1998, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.7686	26.8231
		Platanaki 1.5 km NW of city of Samos	1991, 1993	Bank & Maassen 1998, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.7590	26.9517
		Moni Panagias Kotsika	1991, 1993	Bank & Maassen 1998, as <i>Paralaoma caputspinulae</i>	37.7865	26.9570
		Location 3. Nisyros island. Footpath SE of Palaio-kastro (= Doric castle above Plandraki), in direction of Profitis Ilias	10/1987	Bank & Neuteboom 1988, as <i>Toltecia pusilla</i>	36.6049	27.1321
		Ammouliani island, near a yard, detritus of <i>Olea europaea</i> and <i>Pinus</i> sp. trees	06/2016	Georgiev <i>et al.</i> 2018	40.3183	23.9206
		Mount Pangaio	?	Georgiev 2016	40.8920	24.0939
		Gallikos river by bridge on road 65 between Mandres and Gallikos village	05/2015	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2016	40.8608	22.8937
		Rendina near the mouth in Stavros	05/2015	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2016	40.6588	23.6245
Akropolis Tyritha	1973	Falkner 1974, as <i>Pleuropunctum micropleuros</i>	37.5989	22.7998		
DISCIDAE						
3	<i>Gonyodiscus rotundatus</i>	Kalamata, deposits of river Nedonas	04/2014	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2015, as <i>Discus rotundatus</i>	37.0422	22.1131
		Kalamata, deposits of river Nedonas	06/2018	Reischütz & Reischütz 2019, as <i>Discus rotundatus</i>	37.0430	22.1116
HELICODISCIDAE						
4	<i>Lucilla singleyana</i>	Kalamata, deposits of river Nedonas	04/2014	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2015	37.0422	22.1131
		River deposits of Spercheios N of Kostalexis (W of Lamia, Fthiotida, Greece)	09/2019	Reischütz & Reischütz 2020	38.8679	22.3622
		Litochorion, rocky banks of river Enipeas	07/2006	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2008	40.1069	22.5028
		2. Canal between Boutsis and Patoulia N of Lake Lysimachia	07/2004	Reischütz & Reischütz 2009b, as <i>Lucilla scintilla</i>	38.6114	21.3462
		Gallikos river by bridge on road 65 between Mandres and Gallikos village	05/2015	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2016	40.8608	22.8937
		Rendina near mouth in Stavros	05/2015	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2016	40.6588	23.6245
GASTRODONTIDAE						

Table A1. Continued.

No.	Species	Location	Collection date	Literature reference	Lat. (°N)	Long. (°E)
5	<i>Zonitoides arboreus</i>	River deposits of Spercheios N of Kostalexis (W of Lamia, Fthiotida)	09/2019	Reischütz & Reischütz 2020	38.8679	22.3622
PRISTILOMATIDAE						
6	<i>Hawaiiia minuscula</i>	Bottom of mill stream “Mylonas” in Lefkada W of Lamia, Fthiotida		Reischütz & Reischütz 2020	38.9104	21.9992
		Louros, plant nursery, in a pot of <i>Eucalyptus</i>	08/2003	Reischütz & Reischütz 2009a	39.1607	20.7532
LIMACIDAE						
8	<i>Ambigolimax valentianus</i>	Kafoudi, meadow on S bank of river Axios, under boards Kavros, Crete	07/2010 2011	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2011 Rowson <i>et al.</i> 2014	40.7797 35.3507	22.6138 24.2988
		Skyros	2000–2008	Triantis <i>et al.</i> 2008	38.8504	24.5716
9	<i>Ambigolimax parvipenis</i>	Athens	10/2020	Hutchinson <i>et al.</i> 2022	37.9751	23.7427
BOETTGERILLIDAE						
10	<i>Boettgerilla pallens</i>	Kafoudi, meadow on S bank of river Axios, under boards	07/2010	Reischütz <i>et al.</i> 2011	40.7797	22.6138
AGRIOLIMACIDAE						
11	<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	Kavros, Crete	2011	Rowson <i>et al.</i> 2014	35.3507	24.2988

Table A2. List of iNaturalist observations of alien land snails and slugs recorded from Greece. The numbers in the first column refer to the numbered species in the main text, except for the undetermined species of *Ambigolimax*, which is not provided with a number in the main text.

No.	Species	Observation date	iNaturalist observation (hyperlinked)	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)
PUNCTIDAE					
2	<i>Paralaoma servilis</i>	10/2022	142244725	40.7314	21.8312
		01/2021	68653345	40.6366	22.9729
		12/2020	66294228	40.1859	22.0028
POLYGYRIDAE					
7	<i>Polygyra cereolus</i>	06/2020	51343280	36.4056	28.1834
LIMACIDAE					
—	<i>Ambigolimax</i> sp.*	03/2023	152164189	37.9888	23.6634
		06/2022	120985634	40.1366	23.7493
		09/2017	104114120	41.1432	23.0044
		07/2021	87683425	38.0888	23.9786
		02/2021	70329134	40.6390	22.9632
		11/2020	65765266	38.0175	23.6887
		04/2020	42572950	38.0889	23.9787
		03/2020	40537971	36.3869	28.2137
		02/2020	39805843	38.9731	26.3944
		08/2019	31988701	39.1447	23.8647
		10/2021	98134313	39.6612	20.8552
		10/2020	62837920	40.6224	22.9550
		03/2019	35668830	36.3353	28.1720
		02/2024	198524960	35.3636	24.4850
		02/2023	148005111	35.3610	24.4882
		08/2022	133954385	39.5426	21.4825
		08/2021	96557701	36.3871	28.2134
		04/2021	74066227	36.3808	28.2213
		03/2024	200876058	38.03809	23.8421
		03/2024	200876524	38.03967	23.8445
		03/2024	202554029	39.6732	20.8616
		05/2024	222821960	40.5938	23.0532
		05/2024	219972280	37.9888	23.6634
08/2024	238754956	40.6315	22.9695		
03/2024	152164189	37.9888	23.6634		

*Identified as *Ambigolimax valentianus* in iNaturalist (see main text).